

Consternations over Genetically Designed Products : A Recap

H.K. GARG & JAYA GARG

GOVERNMENT MOTILAL VIGYAN MAHAVIDYALAYA
BHOPAL - 462008 (INDIA)
drharikrishnagarg@gmail.com

ORIENTAL INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY
BHOPAL - 462021 (INDIA)
hjkkrish@gmail.com

There has been a widespread concern in public regarding the hazards of Genetically Designed Food. The introduction of wonder products such as DDT & PCBs and their subsequent withdrawal after encounter with unforeseen problems has undermined public trust in companies that introduce products and in those government agencies which regulate them. There is also a widespread sense that social and technological change is speeding up and people feel powerless to affect this change. Apprehensions on an issue get magnified when the product is food that is being changed.

In 2002, Oregon Ballot Measures gave voters one of the first opportunities in the United States to directly address the issue. The measure, which could have enforced the labeling of genetically engineered foods, failed to pass by a ratio of 7 to 3.

Investigations by the Pew Initiative on Food and Biotechnology showed that Americans' knowledge of genetically modified foods and animals continues to remain low. Despite continuing concerns about GM foods, American consumers do not support banning new uses of the technology, but rather seek an active role from regulators to ensure that new products are safe. A 2010 survey found that over one third of U.S. consumers were very or extremely concerned about GM food.

During 2003 only 2% of Britons were reported to be happy to eat GM foods and more than half of Britons were against GM foods being available to the public.

However, a recent review article of European consumer polls concluded that opposition to GMOs in Europe has been gradually decreasing. Approximately half of European consumers accepted gene technology, particularly when benefits for consumers and for the environment could be linked to GMO products. Many consumers seem unafraid of health risks from GMO products and most European consumers did not actively avoid GMO products while shopping.

Though there is now broad scientific consensus that GE crops on the market are safe enough to eat, yet some scientists and advocacy groups such as Greenpeace and World Wildlife Fund have concerns that GM food may not be safe enough and that contemporary testing regimes are not adequate to ensure sufficient safety. The current communiqué put forth a construal of scientific confab on this international concern.

Key words : GMO, Food hazards, Cisgenic food, Transgenic food.

References:

- **Garg, HK;** Choudhary, A (2011) Anticancer & Anti mutagenic Properties of Medicinal Plants. *National Seminar On Emerging Trends In Biodiversity & Environmental Conservation*, 39.
- **Garg, HK;** Garg, J (2013) Should labeling be enforced on genetically designed products? *National Seminar on Computer Assisted Drug Designing for Green Chemistry*, 20-21.
- **Garg, HK;** Garg, J (2012) Worldwide Endorsement on Genetically Modified Food. *National Seminar on Science for Shaping the Future of India* organized under the auspices of Indian Science Congress Kolkata & M.P. Council of Science & Technology Bhopal, 68.
- **Garg, HK;** Shrivastava, A (2013) Andrographolide induced succinate dehydrogenase activity in isolated mitochondrial fractions from different organ of BALB/c mice. *International Organization for Scientific Research - Journal of Pharmacy & Biological Sciences, USA* 6(4) : 43-45.
- **Garg, HK;** Shrivastava, A (2013) Evaluation and impact of anti-tuberculosis drug. **International Journal of Scientific Research**, 2(7): 20-21.
- **Garg, HK;** Shrivastava, A (2013) Clinical use of andrographolide as a potential drug against vole tuberculosis. **International Journal of Pure & Applied Zoology, USA** 1(3) 223-226.
- **Garg, HK;** Shrivastava, A (2013) Allicin as a potent antibiotic against *E. coli*, *P. vulgaris* and *H. pylori*. **Indian Journal of Applied & Pure Biology** 28 (2) : 213-215.
- **Garg, HK;** Shrivastava, A (2013) Effect of *Andrographis paniculata* on *Aspergillus* and *Rhizopus* species. *Agro-Summit 2013: Changing Scenario of Agriculture in Madhya Pradesh: Prospects & Challenges*. 171/13.
- **Garg, HK;** Shrivastava, A (2013) Allicin as a potent antibiotic against dermal infections. *International Conference on Recent Trends in Applied Sciences with Engineering Applications (SCLS1.7)* 57.

- **Garg, HK;** Shrivastava, A (2013) Effect of Stress on Glucose Metabolism. *National Seminar on Stress & Health Management*, 40.
- **Garg, HK;** Shrivastava, A (2012) Anticancer drugs: Difficulties in development and usages. *National Seminar on Human Papilloma Virus and Control of Cervical Cancer-Current Scenario* (PP-8) 37.
- **Garg, HK;** Shrivastava, A (2012) Evaluation and impact of anti-tuberculosis drug lines against an MDR - *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* isolates *National Seminar on Environmental Conservation & Management*, 12.
- **Garg, HK;** Shrivastava, A; Kalesharia, N (2011) Role of Genetic Research for Identification and Treatment of Cancer. *National Seminar On Emerging Trends In Research & Analysis for Sustainable Development*, 57.
- **Garg, HK;** Shrivastava, A (2011) Growth inhibition of *E.coli*, *P.vulgaris* and *H. pylori* by Acillin. *National Seminar On Emerging Trends In Biodiversity & Environmental Conservation*, 29.
- Shrivastava, A; **Garg, HK** (2013) Application of Nano-technology and Biocomputation for treatment of cancer. **The Pharma Innovation Journal, Ukraine** 2(6) : 63-66.
- Shrivastava, A; **Garg, HK** (2013) Cytotoxic Potential of Andrographolide against Bovine Tuberculosis. International Organization for Scientific Research - **Journal of Pharmacy & Biological Sciences, USA** 8(5) : 01-04.
- Shrivastava, A.; **Garg, HK** (2013) Mycobacterial lipid degrading enzymes as novel drug target against tuberculosis. *National Conference on Innovative & Emerging Trends in Information Technology*. 37.
- Shrivastava, A.; **Garg, HK** (2013) Computer abetted drug design for handling tuberculosis. *National Seminar on Computer Assisted Drug Designing for Green Chemistry*, 21-22.